

Effect of WOKOZIM on lowland rice yields in Maligaya, Nueva Ecija, and Midsayap, Cotabato, 1989 WS and 1990 DS.

Treatment		Grainyield ^a (t/ha)	
NPK (kg/ha)	WOKOZIM (ml/ha)	Maligaya	Midsayap
1989 WS		<i>IR64</i>	<i>IR72</i>
60-30-30	0	2.8 b	3.6 b
60-30-30	450	3.4 ab	4.2 a
90-30-30	0	3.1 ab	3.4 b
90-30-30	450	3.7 a	4.1 a
1990 DS		<i>IR72</i>	<i>IR74</i>
90-30-30	0	4.6 b	2.8 a
90-30-30	450	5.0 ab	3.2 a
120-30-30	0	4.6 b	2.6 a
120-30-30	450	5.2 a	2.9 a

^aMean of four replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by LSD.

30 kg NPK/ha in DS); recommended fertilizer rate + WOKOZIM; farmers' fertilizer rate (90-30-30 kg NPK/ha in WS and 120-30-30 kg NPK/ha in DS); and farmers' fertilizer rate + WOKOZIM. We applied WOKOZIM to IR64 (WS) and IR72 (DS) at Maligaya and IR72 (WS) and IR74 (DS) in Midsayap.

WOKOZIM increased yield 16-21% during WS and 8-14% during DS (see table). We attributed this increase to more tillers, higher percentage of filled grains, and heavier grains. Other agronomic parameters showed no statistical differences among treatments. □

Effect of nitrogen levels and soil moisture conservation practices on rainfed rice

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We studied how six tillage methods and three N application levels affected grain and straw yields of rice during 1990 wet season. The soil was silty-clay loam with pH 5.8, 9.3 g organic C/ha, 502.8 kg available N/ha, 4.7 kg available P/ha, and 272.3 kg available K/ha in the top 15 cm.

The experiment was laid out in split-plot design with three replications. Tillage methods were in the main plots, N levels in the subplots (see table).

Effects of tillage practices and N levels on grain and straw yields of rainfed rice, 1990.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)		Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)	
	Grain	Straw		Grain	Straw
Tillage practices			N levels (kg/ha)		
Dry seeding (DSR)	1.2	3.0	40	1.3	2.8
DSR + halod (H)	1.6	3.4	80	1.5	3.5
DSR with deep tillage (DT)	1.5	3.7	120	1.6	3.8
DSRDT + H	1.7	3.5	LSD(0.05)	1.0	3.3
DSR + lantana mulch (LM)	1.4	3.4			
DSRDT + LM	1.5	3.3			
LSD(0.05)	1.5	ns			

^aHalod is plowing fields with standing water when rice is 15-20 cm.

Dry seeded rice (DSR) with deep tillage + halod (DSRDT + H) produced the most grain at 1.71 t/ha. Tillage

practice did not influence straw yield. Grain and straw yields increased significantly as N rates increased. □

Technical inefficiency of rice production in Chiang Mai, Thailand

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Rice is grown mainly during the wet season (Jun-Oct), followed by dry season (Nov-May) crops, in the lowland irrigated Chiang Mai Valley. Rice yields vary even with the same input levels, suggesting technical inefficiencies in production.

We randomly sampled and interviewed 193 rice farmers using a structured questionnaire. We collected 1989 data from four cropping systems: rice - soybean, rice - potato, rice - tomato, and rice - garlic.

We analyzed the data using the stochastic Cobb-Douglas frontier production model. Per farm rice grain output was the dependent variable. Independent variables were per farm inputs of cropping area, labor, fertilizer, pesticides, and herbicides.

Two error terms were specified: a random error with normal distribution (variation in yield due to random stresses beyond farmers' control, such as bad weather) and a one-sided error with half-normal distribution (loss due to farmer inefficiency).

Farmers averaged 7.5% rice yield loss, meaning the average sampled rice yield

was only 92.5% of potential yield (see table). Rice yield loss to technical inefficiency was more than 10% for 19 farmers. The most inefficient farmer lost 26.1%.

The T-test showed that inefficiency statistics were significant (p = 0.01). Further research, however, is needed to determine if increasing mean yield by 7.5% would be economical through the technical means considered in this analysis. □

Potential and observed rice grain yield in Chiang Mai, Thailand, 1989.^a

Actual yield (t/ha)	4.2
Potential yield (t/ha)	4.6
Yield loss due to technical inefficiency	
Percent	7.5
Amount (kg/ha)	342

^aBased on 193 observations.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.